

AI Based Solutions for Manufacturing Mass Customization

Luis Usatorre^(✉) ,
and Asier Aguayo

Fundacion Tecnalia Research and Innovation, Member of the Basque Research Technology Alliance (BRTA), Mendaro, Spain
luis.usatorre@tecnalia.com

Abstract. This paper analyses how to solve the challenges in the implementation of Mass Customization in manufacturing using Artificial Intelligence agents/services/tools. Considering that humans alone cannot cope with mass customization due to the huge amount of information, it is required AI based solutions that help humans to take decisions. We consider that those AI based solutions must communicate with other AI based solutions in order to obtain a holistic improvement (this is the Multi Agent System concept). More in detail, this paper addresses how to solve the challenges identified when AI based agents use external data coming from outside the company, so a Data Space to guaranteeing a secure data transaction and data ownership and sovereignty is required.

This paper presents the solutions implemented in several projects to address the challenges created by the requirements on a-the implementation and scalability of AI based solutions in Manufacturing, b-for the implementation of multi-Agent AI-based systems and for c-implementing Data Spaces.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence · Manufacturing · Data Spaces · Multi Agent System (MAS) · Value Chain (VC)

1 Introduction

The future of manufacturing in Europe is poised towards mass customization, driven by market variations, supply disruptions, and changes in auxiliary resources (such as energy and water) due to demographic shifts and climate change. While this scenario promises faster fabrication lead times, reduced time-to-market efforts, and improved customer satisfaction [1], it also presents significant challenges related to flexibility, responsiveness, and sustainability.

To address these challenges, this paper presents a solution enhancing inter-organizational information exchange within a Multi-Agent System (MAS) framework. The approach involves integrating various AI-based services for manufacturing and auxiliary processes. Additionally, standardized data, models (using the Asset Administration Shell, AAS) is employed for efficient data storage, while new communication protocols and connectors (such as the International Data Spaces, IDS) facilitate seamless data transactions.

AI-based services, acting as agents, play a crucial role in optimizing manufacturing process parameters, maintenance, and scheduling. These agents consider multi-objective requirements and adapt to the use of novel recycled materials, aligning with circularity objectives. The result is improved accuracy and responsiveness in manufacturing operations.

But when dealing with supply or value chain or when addressing the whole product lifecycle, the data that AI based agents use is coming from many different sources outside the company. In order to guarantee a secure data transaction, guaranteeing the data ownership and sovereignty it is required to implement a Data Space (DS) that permits the seamless data transaction amongst numerous stakeholders.

With this in mind, this paper analyses the requirements that currently exist for these issues, how they interrelate and how they can be addressed. This analysis is guided by the research questions (RQs) presented below:

- RQ1. – What are the requirements for the implementation and scalability of AI based solutions in Manufacturing and in Circularity?
- RQ2. – What are the requirements for a Multi-Agent AI-based system?
- RQ3. – What are the requirements implementing Data Spaces?

As a result, this paper present the challenges addressed when following the requirements and aims also to answer the question *What do Data Spaces (DS) bring to AI applications?*. This question will be discussed as one of the paper conclusions.

The paper is organized as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the theoretical background about DS and AI.
- Section 3 describes the requirements found in previous projects and the experience acquired overcoming them.
- Finally, the paper ends with conclusions and proposals for future research in Sect. 4.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Background on AI in Manufacturing and Circularity

In the EU, manufacturing systems are advanced yet not fully optimized for flexibility and resiliency, particularly in terms of energy and water use. Traditional approaches focus mainly on efficiency and cost, often overlooking the significance of optimizing machine parameter configurations for resource consumption.

There is a gap in integrating these considerations into production planning, which leads to missed opportunities for reducing energy and water usage. Additionally, most existing systems are not designed to dynamically adapt machine settings based on real-time operational data, which could significantly enhance sustainability and operational efficiency. In projects like DIGIPRIME and MASA4AI, the problems of planning and reconfiguration of machines have been addressed to make them more efficient, but this has been done by combining different agents within a factory and without considering data or results coming from outside or essential resources such as water or energy.

Current manufacturing systems in the EU are optimized mainly for efficiency within single entities, lacking in comprehensive Value Chain (VC) integration [2]. This narrow focus results in operational scoreboards and VC assessments do not provide a complete

picture of the supply chain's dynamics and risks. Additionally, existing solutions fall short in considering the stochastic behaviour and risks of the organization's VC, leading to gaps in seamless system performance and optimal resource utilization.

Several studies have proposed different indicators to assess VC, but there is no standardized set of indicators to measure it. Regarding the development of digital tools to assess the VC, the majority of identified tools focused on the human domain [3], while others, such as DHL [4], have worked on a transportation process tool and only for external factors (natural disasters, meteorology, accidents...).

In order to provide a concise overview of the artificial intelligence technologies that will be used in our services, these technologies will be grouped into 4 areas:

- **AI-1: Data Analysis.** This group includes techniques that enable data analysis to enhance users' understanding of its functioning. It encompasses techniques such as data cleaning, univariate analysis, bivariate analysis, statistical inference tests, outlier identification and active learning.
- **AI-2: Machine and Deep Learning.** This group encompasses various algorithms used in classification and regression problems, such as neural networks, convolutional networks, random forests, Support vector machine (SVM), among others.
- **AI-3: Optimization Algorithms.** This group includes algorithms used for modelling and solving single or multi-objective optimization problems. The algorithms belonging to this group include metaheuristic algorithms (such as genetic algorithms, bee colony optimization), mixed-integer linear programming, Bayesian optimization, or deep reinforcement learning.
- **AI-4: Generative Models.** This group includes technologies used to artificially generate data samples, such as Diffusion Models, Variational Autoencoders, and Generative Adversarial Networks.

2.2 Background on Multi Agent Systems (MAS)

Assessing MaaS requires collaboration and data sharing among stakeholders to identify data sources, define data requirements, and develop analytical models that can optimise VC performance and resilience [5]. Currently, however, data is often siloed within companies, preventing other stakeholders from accessing it, and many stakeholders lack the knowledge to analyse the data they have access to; thus, an assessment tool is necessary to identify incentives on how data sharing and data-driven management can improve the transparency, efficiency and resilience of VC activities [6].

Manufacturing Digital Services (or AI based services for manufacturing) have evolved in the last years reaching highest TRLs, being found in many sections of a manufacturing company (production, business, scheduling, purchases, quality...). Nevertheless, the relation of different agents to act coordinated as an integrated holistic system is still a pending issue.

An attempt to create a holistic [7] (MAS) was addressed in MAS4AI project, taking AAS and JANUS platform as the technology bricks for the seamless interaction of agents. But the technology is still at very low TRLs and based at machine and process level but not at VC level. Meanwhile, TRICK project addressed the data interaction of materials and products based on the DPP.

The main limitations for the creation of a MAS involving manufacturing data owners and external service providers were: i) the lack of standardized data due to the lack of confidence of manufacturers in data transactions, and ii) the lack of confidence of technology and service providers in uploading their developments in a central platform. AAS information contains data in motion and at rest. While some information is nominal and can be public, other is confidential as well as the know-how of the manufacturing companies. The latest information must be restricted to specific stakeholders.

2.3 Background on Data Spaces

A Data Space refers to the physical or virtual space where data is stored, transferred and managed. It can include databases, data warehouses, data lakes, and other data storage systems. The focus is not only on the storage and organization of data but also on the data transaction and data monetization.

On top of it, a data space is a more comprehensive solution that provides not only data storage but also tools for data integration, transformation, analysis, and visualization. It enables organizations to manage their entire data lifecycle, from data acquisition to data consumption. A data space often includes APIs, connectors, and other tools that allow data to be easily accessed and shared across different systems, applications and tools for managing the entire data lifecycle across different entities, facilities or companies.

Circular Data Spaces and Data Spaces for circularity refer to Data Spaces designed to support circular economy principles, with a stronger focus on circularity and optimized for circular data management.

The main stakeholders on a DS ecosystem can be clustered in the following families according to the Design Principles for Data Spaces, Position Paper, v1.0. April 2021 [8]:

- **Data owner:** Data owner is responsible for the quality of acquired and primary processed data, in all related to accuracy, reliability, resolution, availability, etc. Decides how its data can be used by third parties.
- **Data provider:** Collects and prepares data and provides them to others on behalf of a Data owner. This role remains close to Data owner and as a part of the agreement and to improve its current business, it may use apps and results which uses collected data. Manufacturing SMEs will be able to share industrial process data with the value chain in a secure way in order to get revenues through it.
- **Data processor:** It is the expert company who knows the real value of the data obtained from the provider and who can holistically preview business possibilities which cannot be accessed by Data owner. We can distinguish two roles:
- **Data Transformers and service providers:** Tech companies will be able to develop apps in order to provide services to consumers based on the data of providers.
- **Data/service consumers:** Industrial companies will be able to improve their services based on third parties' data.
- **Brokers/Operators/DS Managers:** It is the entity to provide infrastructure needed for all the data transactions which are about to occur, as software systems, hardware or data-processing tools. It is also responsibility of the Marketplace operator the governance of all support services, permissions, log files. They are needed, as a new business sort of service, to get things happen in the complete scenario.

3 Methods

In this section, the requirements for the implementation, how they interrelate and how they can be addressed are presented. This analysis is guided by the research questions (RQs) presented below:

- RQ1. – What are the requirements for the implementation and scalability of AI based solutions in Manufacturing and in Circularity?
- RQ2. – What are the requirements for a Multi-Agent AI-based system?
- RQ3. – What are the requirements implementing Data Spaces?

3.1 RQ1. – What are the Requirements for the Implementation and Scalability of AI in Manufacturing and Circularity?

The requirements for an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system to run are:

- Data availability: AI systems require large amounts of high-quality relevant data to train on.
- Data consistency: To avoid data inconsistency some technical requirements for an AI system may include:
 - Data pre-processing techniques; such as data cleaning, normalization, and feature scaling, which can help to reduce data inconsistencies and improve the accuracy of predictions [9].
 - Data augmentation techniques; such as data synthesis and data sampling can be used to increase the amount of training data and improve the diversity of the data set, reducing the risk of overfitting and improving the accuracy of the model [10].
 - Data quality assurance techniques; such as data profiling and data validation, can be used to identify and address data inconsistencies, reducing the risk of errors and improving the accuracy of the model.
 - Data governance policies and procedures can be also put in place to ensure that data is consistent, accurate, and reliable, reducing the risk of errors and improving the performance of the AI system.
- Sufficient data for training: One straightforward solution to the lack of data is to collect more data through various methods such as web scraping, crowdsourcing, and data partnerships. Further technical requirements for an AI system, to address this challenge may include:
 - Transfer learning: since such techniques, can be used to train an AI system on a related task or data set and then transfer the learned knowledge to the target task or data set, reducing the amount of training data required.
 - Active learning: since such techniques can also be used to selectively choose which data points to label and use for training, reducing the amount of labelled data required [11].

- Programming skills and Algorithms availability: to analyse and interpret complex data patterns, make decisions and learn from new data. It requires expertise in programming, machine learning (ML), and software engineering: Programming languages: Python, Java, etc. [12]; Data processing through the use of libraries such as Pandas, NumPy, and SciPy. Machine learning libraries such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Scikit-learn provide pre-built algorithms and functions [13].
- Computing power: to process large amounts of data, run complex algorithms, re-train the deployed models and to analyse and learn from large data sets. Hardware such as Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), Tensor Processing Units (TPUs), or Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). In addition, large amounts of memory to store and process data efficiently using high-capacity Random Access Memory (RAM) or Solid-State Drives (SSDs). To store large datasets and trained models, using hard disk drives or Network-Attached Storage (NAS) devices. Moreover, high-power supplies to support processing requirements using high-wattage power supplies or redundant power supplies [14].

And the functional/performance requirements for an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system are:

- Accuracy: AI systems must be accurate and reliable in their predictions and decisions;
- Transparency and explainability: Users should be able to understand how the system arrived at its decisions and what factors were considered in the process.
- Security and privacy: AI systems must be secure and protect user privacy
- Scalability: AI systems should be able to scale up or down to accommodate changes in data volume or user demand without sacrificing performance or accuracy.
- Integration: AI systems must be able to integrate with other systems and applications in a seamless and efficient manner, to ensure that they can be used effectively within larger workflows and processes.

3.2 RQ2. – What are the Requirements for a Multi-agent AI-Based System?

As stated before, a Multi Agent System (MAS) is a system that permits the interaction of several agents working together to obtain holistic improvement. The main requirements are:

- Well-identified goals: Setting clear goals is a critical requirement for AI systems to produce consistently accurate and useful results. It requires Appropriate evaluation metrics (e.g., KPIs), Domain expertise to obtain a Well-defined problem statement and User feedback: to refine and adjust the goals of the AI system over time.
- Managing exceptions when an AI systems, fails to operate as expected. Addressing Robust error handling, Monitoring: its own behaviour and log any exceptions that occur. Even analysing exceptions and identifying the root causes of errors. And providing Rigorous testing to ensure that the system can handle a wide range of exceptions and edge cases.
- Managing limitations: while AI systems provide advanced capabilities to the deployed systems, some limitations apply. While the AI systems will be assessed for their accuracy and performance, it is expected that in some very rare cases, specifically on extremely rare circumstances where the system has not been exposed before, it

is possible for a system to produce an inaccurate result. Constant training of the AI systems ensures a smooth operation, and explainability techniques as well as casual analysis can further assist with preventing and correcting accuracies.

- Multi-objective factors weighting: to find the best possible solutions for multiple conflicting objectives. Defining clear objectives aligned with the goals of the organization or users and weigh and prioritize multiple objectives, considering the relative importance of each one.
- Transparency: The AI system should be transparent, with clear documentation and explanations of how it works, what data it uses, and how it makes decisions. This can help users and developers understand the system's limitations [15].
- Validation and verification: The system should be tested and validated to ensure that it performs as expected and that its limitations are well understood. This can involve techniques such as validation testing, sensitivity analysis, and stress testing [16].
- Continuous monitoring and evaluation: The system should be continuously monitored and evaluated to detect any changes in its behaviour or performance. This can involve techniques such as drift detection, model retraining, and model updating [17].
- Human oversight: AI systems should be designed with human oversight in mind, allowing humans to intervene when necessary and ensuring that the system's decisions are fair, transparent, and aligned with ethical and legal frameworks.

3.3 RQ3. – What are the Requirements Implementing DS?

There are two types of requirements in a Data Space: Technical (like Interoperability) and business (like Trustworthy and data monetization) requirements. In the following points, the System requirements (in general) are presented.

Technical Requirements:

- Connectivity: to support trust, security, and data sovereignty not devoted only to ensure the communication or data exchange, but also to expand partnerships and value creation. The IDS Connector is the focal point for securely manage data and its interchange among stakeholders, but keeping the control in hands of the data owner. Permit to trace every piece of data, knowing its origin and checking its quality. To control all options, a vocabulary provider offers ontologies, reference data models, metadata on core data and complete de information of the datasets which are moved and processed along every interaction [18].
- Data filtering and aggregation: To ensure privacy of sensitive data, its processing (e.g., filtering, anonymization, aggregation or analysis) should take place as close to the data source as possible and performed by the backend services or Applications. Only data intended for being made available to other Participants should be offered by Connectors.
- Data storage: a Data Space does not require central data storage capabilities, It pursues the idea of decentralization of data storage, which means that data physically remains with the respective data owner until it is transferred to a trusted party. This approach requires a comprehensive description of each data source and the value and usability of data for other companies, combined with the ability to integrate domain-specific data vocabularies [19].

- **Trusted Data transaction:** reassuring participants that other participants really are who they claim to be and that they comply with defined rules/agreements. This can be achieved by organisational measures (e.g., certification or verified credentials like in GAIA X) or technical measures (e.g., remote attestation like IDSA DAPS) [20].
- **Decision support or actuation:** data analysis and decision support systems followed by the possibility to actuate events directly in the real environment.

Business Requirements:

- **Data monetization:** Data Spaces should provide a structure for defining and enforcing agreements on the use of data (including potential monetization of both data provision and data use).
- **Data business model:** in a Data Space, actors providing and/or consuming data, as well as software vendors need to set agreements and then maintained over time [21].
- **Data sovereignty** is the capability of an individual or organisation to self-determine their data. Through Data Sovereignty Agreements and Industrial Agreements. The final “Study on technological and economic analysis of industry agreements in current and future digital value chain” [22] pointed out that there is a widespread consensus over the importance of such agreements for the development of fertile data sharing environment and fruitful Data Spaces for the manufacturing domain. From the point of view of data sovereignty, IDS Identity Provider module identifies and register who is playing when, how and with whom. This sort of register is a whole logbook of what is really happening and the history of all data transactions [23].
- **Trustworthy:** the lack of trust among the industrial players and stakeholders is inter-related with the regulatory uncertainties, the protection of commercially sensitive and personal data, doubts and concerns on how data will be used or reused when they are further aggregated, the evolving regulatory framework legal landscape on the data sharing operations, on the integrity of the systems used to collect, or be related to the issues relating to the protection of commercially sensitive information. Likewise, the collaboration within a Data Space are often hampered by the fear of losing the competitive advantage or the negotiation power when disclosing business information. In view of fostering trust building and access to data it is recommended that new approaches, such as the data trust structures and approaches [24], are explored. The data trust approaches could also help in distributing the benefits arising from data-sharing more equitably, including monetary benefits.

Data ownership: represent a major obstacle to the Data Space for enabling the sharing of circular information about materials and products towards and should be addressed in the Data Sovereignty Agreements regard [24, 25].

- **Data quality:** regards the lack of clarity on the circumstances under which liability may be incurred for damages due to inaccurate data. Such uncertainty has a relevant impact on the willingness of industry actors to enter into a data sharing environment and Data Space. it is possible that the datasets used to train the AI system contain personal data, as well as it is possible that the technology itself violates the right to

privacy in its functioning, often in an unforeseeable manner. Data pools combining data and analysis might reveal unexpected information.

4 Challenges Addressed and Research

This section presents the challenges addressed and the research carried out when following previous requirements and aims also to answer the question What do Data Spaces (DS) bring to AI applications?

Considering that Manufacturing mass customization affects the Process, the production chain and the company, this section has been separated accordingly.

4.1 Challenges and Research at Manufacturing Process Level

As presented on this paper, at the moment there are numerous AI based agents addressing manufacturing optimization. But these tools apply mainly at process level. For instance, TECNALIA has developed AI based services for improving manufacturing or auxiliary processes like metal machining, plastic extrusion, welding, robot programming, predictive maintenance or production scheduling optimization according to the requirements described on previous chapters.

Results obtained are satisfactory with a clear improvement on the KPIs defined in each case: Improving efficiency; Enhancing decision-making, Personalizing experiences, Increasing revenue, Reducing costs, Improving quality and Explainability.

The challenge is that a company is composed of many different manufacturing processes and all are interrelated.

4.2 Challenges and Research at Manufacturing Chain Level

The next challenge has been the integration of several agents in a holistic system, where AI services interact one with each other to obtain a holistic approach. As presented in figure below, our research has been directed towards a structured way of storing data and organizing agents. AAS, JANUS and KAFKA have been the tools applied to obtain the desired results. In the following figure (Fig. 1), TECNALIA presents the solution applied in the MAS4AI project considering previous requirements to create a MAS to optimize grinding wheels manufacturing performance integrating tooling selection, machining parameters optimization and scheduling recalculation and optimization. In this solution, data are stored in different types of data bases (MySQL, Elastic Search, Postgre), the AI based tools are distributed in different Python frameworks (LMS, Tecnalía, Sisteplant) and the AAS of the agents are on a Basyx framework.

4.3 Challenges and Research at Company Level

But to extend the MAS solution, applied at company level, to the value chain level requires the implementation of a Data Space for the seamless (secure and trusted) transaction of data. As mentioned before, DS implementation requires to address two aspects: technical and business. Both aspects are important. While the business aspects are still at

Fig. 1. Implementation of a Multi Agent System

an embryonary level, the technical requirements have been already addressed and today, Data Spaces have been tested by TECNALIA on a peer to peer basis (MARKET4.0, AI REGIO) and using different connectors (TRUE, EDC...) according to the classic standard framework IDSA RA (Reference Architecture).

Fig. 2. AI REGIO DS implementation

Fig. 3. MARKET4.0 DS implementation

But the solution to the technical requirements is still uncertain and protocols and standards are not yet clear. At the moment these are the main technical challenges we are facing:

- DS Connectors (EDC, TRUE, DSC, SOVITY, EDC GAIA X type,...) do not interact one with each other
- Most connectors do not interact with previous or latter versions of the same connector. As an example, EDC does not interact with TRUE. TRUE does not with SOVITY, SOVITY does not with DSC... and none of them with the central modules (i.e. Broker, clearing House, Identity Provider...)of the others.
- Some connectors early versions are deprecated
- Connectors do not cope with streaming data transactions
- Connectors do not work on a multipeer environment. As an example, a data receiving connector cannot be connected to several data emitting connectors. The receiver is not able to handle the information. So the connection today must be peer to peer (connector to connector) and not multipeer.

The solution to solve these issues is being applied in CIRC TWAIN. Connectors are used to solve the business aspects (data control) while the pure data transaction takes place out of the connectors and directly between data repositories. This solution permits to solve most of the previously identified technical constraints (see Figs. 2, 3, and 4).

Fig. 4. Eclipse DS components

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This section presents the conclusions on our research.

On the first hand, we can conclude that Manufacturing Mass customization cannot be implemented without involving different levels of the company (process, production chain and value chain).

We can also conclude that to address the upper levels (value chain) it is required to have solved the lower ones (process).

A third conclusion is that a secure, trustworthy data transaction is essential. But on top of the technical challenges, it is also essential to address the business aspects and build trust among the industrial players and ensure a greater cooperation among them in distributed value chains to set common frameworks and rules for data sharing. This includes the creation of the conditions to enable such players to build trustworthy relationships and of a trusted environment for data sharing within and across industries. And, as a summary, DATA SPACES provide the infrastructure to improve holistically the manufacturing plant through MAS where each AI based AGENT Improve each manufacturing process.

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